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8 **Legacy effects of leguminous green manure crops on the weed seed**
9 **bank in organic crop rotations**

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by

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Short title: **Weed seed bank depletion**

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25 **Abstract**

26

27 Leguminous green manure crops are important for accumulating nitrogen by means of biological
28 nitrogen fixation and for building up soil fertility in organic arable cropping systems. Whole-year
29 green manure crops are also known to deplete the soil weed seed bank, e.g. by decaying and
30 predation, but there is uncertainty about the magnitude of the legacy effect after termination of the
31 green manure crop. This study sampled soil for weed seed bank assessment upon termination of a
32 two-year leguminous green manure crop and then one, two and three years afterwards. The samples
33 were taken from two five-year crop rotations (2011-2015) in a long-term organic crop rotation
34 experiment in Denmark. One rotation (O2) had a two-year green manure crop followed by three
35 years of annual cash crops, and the other rotation (O4) consisted only of annual cash crops, with
36 four crop sequences in both rotations represented every year. In general, the weed seed bank of
37 rotation O2 was 54 % lower than O4, with 5,475 seeds m⁻² versus 11,967 seeds m⁻². Similarly the
38 aboveground amount of weed biomass in O2 was lower than in O4 over the course of the five years.
39 The legacy effect of the green manure crop showed a negative exponential rise in weed seed
40 numbers with the increase in years after termination of the green manure crop. A biennial
41 leguminous green manure crop can mitigate weed problems in organic annual crops. This effect
42 adds to the benefits of including nitrogen fixing leys in crop rotations with limited access to animal
43 manures.

44

45 **Keywords:** Lucerne, grass-clover, broadleaved weeds, grass weeds, seed bank depletion, seed
46 decay

47

48 1. Introduction

49

50 The composition of crop rotations and the sequence in which crops are grown greatly affect
51 the weed flora (Teasdale, 2018). A well-designed crop rotation is probably the most effective
52 cultural method for reducing a weed problem within a relatively short period. Annual weed species
53 that may have become particularly numerous following frequent cropping of crop species with a
54 similar life cycle can be disrupted by changing to crops with different life traits (Teasdale, 2018).
55 Inevitably, crop diversification also introduces additional disrupting factors such as weed control
56 methods and timing, fertilisation, harvest time, tillage methods and timing (Liebman and Dyck,
57 1993). For example, the summer annual species *Chenopodium album* L. can proliferate when spring
58 cereals are frequently grown since its seed germination and growth habit coincide with those of the
59 crops (Håkansson, 2003). Disruption of *C. album* can be achieved through annual winter crops
60 established in the autumn. Most seeds of *C. album* do not germinate in the autumn and the few that
61 do are likely to be killed by winter frost. The general loss of weed seeds in soil over time combined
62 with two or three years of winter crops in a row, preventing the input of new seeds, causes the seed
63 bank of *C. album* to decline (Håkansson, 2003).

64 Diversification in crop rotation plays an important part in weed management in organic crop
65 production (Kolb and Gallandt, 2012). A balanced composition of crops in the rotation, where
66 spring-sown and autumn-sown crops are grown in equal proportions, normally prevents the build-
67 up of large weed populations in which a few species occur in great numbers (Blackshaw et al.,
68 2007). Weed species that are either summer or winter annuals usually respond to balanced rotations
69 and become manageable. Nevertheless, many species exhibit both summer and winter annual
70 growth characteristics, for example *Stellaria media* (L.) Vill. and *Tripleurospermum perforatum*
71 (Mérat) M. Laínz, and may not decline in abundance just by balancing the seasonal growth habit of

72 annual crops (Melander et al., 2017). Methods to diversify the crop rotation, other than a change in
73 seasonal crop establishment, are required in order to reduce this type of weed species as well. The
74 general weed pressure is reduced with more complex crop compositions, while weed species
75 richness and diversity usually become greater (Teasdale, 2018).

76 Whole-year green manure crops consisting of perennial legumes either grown solely or in
77 mixtures with grasses offer another element of diversification that will affect the entire weed seed
78 bank. Such crops are particularly effective if they last for more than a year (Sjursen, 2001). Annual
79 weeds disappear quickly in well-established green manure stands, particularly if the canopy is
80 regularly mown. The absence of tillage and the re-growth of the green manure after cutting make
81 the establishment of annual weeds difficult (Davies et al., 1997). The input of new weed seeds into
82 the seed bank is minimal during the lifetime of a green manure, and the relatively short longevity of
83 most annual weed seeds (Bohan et al., 2011) can result in a substantial reduction in the weed seed
84 bank. Perennial forage crops of two or three years' duration are known to reduce weed problems in
85 dairy production systems and increase the yields of subsequent crops (Rasmussen et al., 1998).

86 Organic arable farms with limited access to animal manures can include whole-year green
87 manures in the crop rotation to reduce weed problems and enhance soil fertility through biological
88 nitrogen (N) fixation and carbon sequestration (Olesen et al. 2007, 2009). However, growers are
89 usually reluctant to grow green manure crops due to their limited short-term cash value. The
90 magnitude of weed seed bank reduction in the first year following full-season legumes and legume-
91 grass crops have previously been reported, mainly for annual broadleaved species (Albrecht, 2005;
92 Sjursen, 2001; Sjursen et al., 2012; Teasdale et al., 2004). However, the rate of weed re-infestation
93 in annual crops in the years following green manures remains uncertain and lacks quantification.
94 This information could help growers with limited access to animal manure consider the inclusion of

95 whole-year green manure crops in their crop rotations to improve soil fertility and reduce severe
96 weed problems.

97 The objective of this study was to quantify the effect of a two-year leguminous green manure
98 crop in the crop rotation on the weed seed bank, weed species richness and weed diversity. The
99 investigation was undertaken in a long-term organic crop rotation experiment that allowed a
100 comparison of a five-year crop rotation including a biennial green manure crop with a five-year
101 rotation consisting of annual cash crops only. More importantly, the experiment allowed the study
102 of weed re-infestation 0, 1, 2 and 3 years after termination of the biennial green manure crop. It was
103 hypothesised that there would still be a significant legacy effect on the weed seed bank three years
104 after termination of the two-year green manure crop.

105

106 **2. Materials and methods**

107

108 *2.1. Crop rotation experiment*

109

110 Soil and biomass samples were taken from the organic crop rotation experiment at
111 Foulumgaard (56°30'N, 09°35'E) in Central Jutland, Denmark. Several papers treating different
112 cropping subjects have been published from this experiment (e.g. Olesen et al., 2007, 2009;
113 Melander et al., 2016; De Notaris et al., 2018). The experiment was commenced in 1996 and the
114 design is explained in more details in Olesen et al. (2000). Melander et al. (2016) elucidated the
115 dynamics of perennial weeds in the experiment for the period 1997-2008 and found that *Cirsium*
116 *arvense* (L.) Scop. was strongly suppressed when the crop rotation included a one-year grass-clover
117 subjected to mowing. Rasmussen et al. (2006) described the weed flora during the first course of the

118 rotations (1997-2000) and found no major weed proliferation during the first four years, mainly
119 thanks to physical weed control interventions.

120 Two organic crop rotations were established in 1997. The major difference between
121 rotations was that one rotation (O2) had a one-year green manure crop (grass-clover) while the
122 other (O4) had an annual grain legume crop. The purpose of the legumes in O2 and O4 was to
123 provide N input through biological N fixation (Pandey et al., 2017). The experiment has three
124 experimental treatments with (i) rotations combined with (ii) cover crop [with (+CC) and without (-
125 CC)], and (iii) manure [with (+M) and without (-M)] arranged in a complete factorial design with
126 two replicates (blocks) every year. The plot size was 12 × 18 m and the use of just two replicates is
127 explained in Chirinda et al. (2010). Only the manured treatments (+M/-CC, +M/+CC) were
128 included in the present study. The non-manured treatment did not reflect current crop management
129 in organic farming. The rotation cycles and crops grown in both crop rotations O2 and O4 for 1997-
130 2008 are explained in Melander et al. (2016). However, the crop rotations were changed in 2010 to
131 reflect a five-year rotation cycle, with O2 having a legume-based green manure crop lasting for two
132 years before being terminated (Table 1). Crop rotation O4 still had a grain legume either solely
133 (entry 1) or in mixture with spring barley (entries 2, 3 and 4), but this time also a highly competitive
134 crop hemp (*Cannabis sativa* L.) to help suppress weed growth (Table 1).

135 Each crop rotation had four crop sequence entries (Table 1), meaning that sampling was
136 performed in 32 plots in total (2 rotations × 2 cover crop treatments × 4 entries × 2 replicates = 32
137 plots). Due to the original experimental design, four crops were represented each year, but with all
138 the plots receiving the full crop sequence for five years (2011-2015). In rotation O2, the crops were
139 spring wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.), potato (*Solanum tuberosum* L.) and spring barley (*Hordeum*
140 *vulgare* L.) with undersown lucerne (*Medicago sativa* L.) or grass-clover (a mixture consisting
141 mainly of perennial ryegrass (*Lolium perenne* L.), white clover (*Trifolium repens* L.) and red clover

142 (*Trifolium pratense* L.). The crops in rotation O4 were spring oat (*Avena sativa* L.), faba bean
143 (*Vicia faba* L.), hemp (*Cannabis sativa* L.) and a mixture of peas (*Pisum sativum* L.) and spring
144 barley, termed ‘pea:barley’. The lucerne and grass-clover mixture for green manure in O2 was
145 undersown in spring barley and later ploughed in spring at the time of termination. All cropping
146 procedures followed the Danish guidelines for organic farming. The lucerne and grass-clover in
147 rotation O2 were cut and the plant materials removed from the plots two to three times per growing
148 season, i.e. in May, July and at the end of August. The concept was to use the cuttings for biogas
149 production, and to return an equivalent amount of N in digestate to the cropping system (Brozyna et
150 al., 2009). The cuttings were thus regarded as a mobile fertilisation source meant for distribution at
151 the farm level, for example to other fields within the crop rotation. For the remainder of this paper,
152 however, the lucerne and grass-clover crops are named ‘green manure crops’.

153 Cover crops were either undersown in May or following the harvest of potato and the main
154 crop in cases where perennial weeds needed to be controlled by stubble cultivation. Mouldboard
155 ploughing in spring was the primary tillage method to incorporate cover crop biomass and to
156 prepare the soil before sowing the main crop. A cover crop mixture of perennial ryegrass (*Lolium*
157 *perenne* L.), chicory (*Chicorium intybus* L.), white clover and red clover was used for undersowing
158 in both rotations O2 and O4, whereas a mixture of winter rye (*Secale cereale* L.), winter vetch
159 (*Vicia villosa* Roth) and winter oilseed rape (*Brassica napus* L.) was used for post-harvest
160 establishment.

161 Animal manure was applied in the treatments receiving manure (+M) at the N rates shown in
162 Table 1. Manure was not applied to green manure crops, grain legume crops or legume:cereal
163 mixtures.

164

165 *2.2. Management of annual weeds*

166

167 Weed harrowing and occasionally inter-row hoeing were applied in cereals and grain legumes
168 for the control of annual weeds. Potato ridges were tilled once or twice using a rotary cultivator to
169 control annual weeds and maintain the ridges. Post-harvest cultivation using a stubble cultivator
170 with goosefoot shares was generally conducted in plots without cover crops after the grain legume
171 crops, cereal crops (other than spring barley with undersown grass-clover) and potato crops. The
172 cultivator was also used when green manure crops were terminated, and occasionally also in plots
173 with cover crops.

174

175 *2.3. Weed seed bank estimation*

176

177 Soil samples were collected in mid-October 2015 from all 32 plots in rotations O2 and O4
178 using an auger with a 50 mm diameter. Ten samples were taken from the plough layer (0-20 cm) in
179 each plot and were then mixed, placed in plastic bags and stored at 4 °C in darkness. The soil
180 samples were later placed in polystyrene boxes and set for germination in a glasshouse at the
181 Department of Agroecology, Aarhus University. The preparation of the boxes and the germination
182 procedure followed that described in Scherner et al. (2016). Germination was completed in late
183 October 2016, providing a germination period of one year. Total number of emerged weed
184 seedlings per box were obtained by regular counting across the year and the data are presented as
185 total number of germinable weed seeds m⁻² of the plough layer.

186

187 *2.4. Assessment of annual weed biomass*

188

189 Aboveground biomass of annual weeds was recorded at the end of June for all crops and for
190 the years 2011-2015, except for the green manure crops in O2. Biomass samples were not taken in
191 2010. Three 0.25 m² quadrats were randomly placed in each plot and all aboveground plant material
192 within each quadrat was cut at ground level. Annual weeds were separated from other plant material
193 and the weed biomass was oven-dried for 24 h at 80 °C to obtain dry matter (DM).

194

195 2.5. Data analyses

196

197 The number of germinable weed seeds m⁻² was analysed using a generalised linear mixed
198 model with a Poisson distribution of errors. Fixed effects were crop rotation, entry point and cover
199 crop, with block as the random term. General linear mixed models with normally distributed data
200 were used to test the fixed effects of crop rotation, entry point and cover crop on the dry matter of
201 annual weeds and on species richness (i.e. the total number of species observed per plot), the
202 Shannon's diversity index (H_{SH}) and the Shannon's evenness index (E_{SH}). H_{SH} was calculated as
203 follows:

$$204 \quad H_{SH} = - \sum_{i=1}^S P_i (\ln P_i) \quad (1)$$

205 where

$$206 \quad P_i = \frac{N_i}{N_{total}} \quad (2)$$

207 where N_i is the number of individuals of species i , N_{total} is the total number of individuals per soil
208 sample and S is the total number of species found. Subsequently E_{SH} was calculated using the
209 following equation:

$$210 \quad E_{SH} = \frac{H_{SH}}{\ln S} \quad (3)$$

211

212 The random terms year, block and year \times block were included in the analyses on weed biomass
213 since results from the period 2011-2015 were included. The biomass data represented a time series
214 with recordings made over time in the same plots. This was accounted for by including year as a
215 repeated effect and plot as the subject with the assumption of an autoregressive correlation structure
216 and variance between years. For the analyses on species richness, H_{SH} and E_{SH} , block was the only
217 random term. The parameters of the linear models were estimated using residual likelihood
218 estimations. Models were simplified by excluding non-significant effects based on likelihood ratio
219 tests and Akaike's information criterion (Akaike, 1974). Calculations on the seed bank data were
220 made with the GLIMMIX procedure of SAS that features a Poisson distribution (SAS release 9.4,
221 SAS Institute Inc., Cary, N.C.). For the biomass data and species indices, calculations were
222 performed using the MIXED procedure of SAS with means calculated as least square means (LSM).
223 Pair-wise comparisons between LSMs were based on t -tests, with probability values adjusted
224 according to the Tukey method. Significant differences between means were achieved when $P <$
225 0.05. The denominator degrees of freedom (DDF) in F -tests and t -tests for mean separations were
226 calculated according to Kenward and Rodger (1997). Homogeneity of variances was ensured by
227 data transformation whenever necessary.

228 The relationship between the seed content (SC) in rotation O2 and the number of years (YR)
229 since the last green manure crop was grown was described using a curvilinear equation:

230

$$231 \quad SC = SB[1 + (1 - \exp^{-bYR})] \quad (4)$$

232

233 where SB is the number of germinable seeds at the time of termination of the green manure crop
234 and b is the rate of increase in the seed bank with increasing YR. YR corresponds to the entry points
235 in Table 1: YR = 0 (entry 1); YR = 1 (entry 2); YR = 2 (entry 4); YR = 3 (entry 3). The termination

236 of green manure crops was considered to occur by the end of October in the second year of the
237 green manure crop period. Curve-fitting was accomplished by the NLIN procedure in SAS. A test of
238 whether cover crop affected the parameters in Eq. (4) was undertaken by comparing a full model, in
239 which both parameters SB and b were considered to be dependent on cover crop, and a reduced
240 model where they were assumed to be equal for the two cover crop treatments. Block effects were
241 assumed to affect only the general weed seed bank level (parameter SB). An F -test was used to
242 identify significance between the two models according to the sum of squares reduction test
243 described by Brown and Rothery (1993).

244

245 **3. Results**

246

247 *3.1. Weed species richness and diversity*

248

249 Twenty-eight and 29 different weed species in total were recorded in rotations O2 and O4,
250 respectively (Table 2). Only crop rotation affected species richness significantly, with O4 having
251 more species on average than O2 (Table 3). However, the Shannon's diversity index (H_{SH}) and the
252 Shannon's evenness index (E_{SH}) did not differ between the two crop rotations. The interaction
253 between crop rotation and entry point was the only significant effect seen for the two indices (Table
254 3). H_{SH} and E_{SH} did not differ for the four entry points in rotation O2, while in O4 the two indices in
255 entry point 2 were significantly lower than those for the other three entry points.

256

257 *3.2. Numbers of germinable weed seeds*

258

259 The total number of germinated seeds was affected by all factors: crop rotation, entry point and
260 cover crop (Table 4). Rotation O4 generally had more than twice as many germinable seeds as O2
261 (Table 5), but crop rotation interacted with the other two factors. Cover crops had no influence on
262 the total content of germinable seeds in O2 (Fig. 1). The seed abundance in O2 increased with the
263 number of years since the last green manure crop was grown, irrespective of the presence of a cover
264 crop (Fig. 2 and Table 6). The number of germinable seeds increased by 33 % one year after the last
265 green manure crop, and by 69 % after three years.

266 Cover crops interacted more strongly with entry point in rotation O4 (Fig. 1), where no cover
267 crop resulted in markedly more germinable seeds for entry points 2 and 4, while the opposite was
268 true for entry point 1.

269 The two principal dicotyledonous species *S. media* and *Capsella bursa-pastoris* (L.) Medik
270 and the genus *Veronica spp.* were the main species that determined the effects on the total number
271 of germinated weed seeds (Tables 2 and 4). In contrast, species in the genus *Poa spp.* behaved in
272 the opposite way to the other principal species, with the most germinable seeds found in rotation O2
273 (Table 2). Compared to the treatments without a cover crop, cover crops reduced the seed bank of
274 *Poa spp.* in O2 by 58 % ($P < 0.0001$) and in O4 by 42 % ($P < 0.0001$) (data not shown).

275

276 3.3. Aboveground biomass of annual weeds

277

278 The biomass of annual weeds was responsive in the period 2011-2015, with significant
279 differences between the experimental factors (Table 7). Rotation O4 had twice as much weed
280 biomass as O2 when averaging the entire period 2011-2015, but the differences between the
281 treatments were not as pronounced as those for germinable seeds (Fig. 3). The aboveground
282 biomass of annual weeds did not correlate well with the seed bank data for total seed germination

283 when averaging biomass data for the years: a) 2015 only; b) 2014 and 2015; c) 2013, 2014 and
284 2015; and d) 2012, 2013, 2014 and 2015. However, there was a general correlation ($P = 0.0049$)
285 between the seed bank data and weed biomass when averaging weed biomass across the years e)
286 2011, 2012, 2013, 2014 and 2015 (Fig. 4).

287

288 **4. Discussion**

289

290 Rotation O2 did not have the expected greater diversity of weed species (Meiss et al., 2010),
291 where new perennial weed species might have been expected to occur in the perennial phase of the
292 rotation. The cutting and subsequent re-growth of the green manure crop created a dense sod in
293 which new species were unable to establish in any noteworthy numbers. Similarly, Sjursen (2001)
294 did not observe greater species richness following a three-year ley period; in contrast, the species
295 number declined from approximately twenty species to just eight. Apart from the difference in crop
296 growth length between the two rotations (annual versus perennial crops), rotation O2 could not be
297 said to be more diverse than O4. Rotation O4 had four crop types (spring cereals, potato, pulses
298 (including pulse/cereal mixture) and hemp) and O2 only three (spring cereals, potato and green
299 manures). Neither rotation had any autumn-sown crops.

300 The weed seed bank in rotation O2 was 52 % smaller than in O4. Sjursen (2001) estimated the
301 weed seed bank the year following a three-year organic grass-clover ley to be 59 % smaller than the
302 seed bank after a three-year period with annual organic crops in Norway. Albrecht (2005) found
303 that a one-year grass-clover ley in the transition from conventional to organic cropping reduced the
304 weed seed bank by 39 % in comparison with the magnitude of the seed bank before commencing
305 the conversion. The duration of the green manure crop is important for preventing new weed seeds
306 from entering the seed bank and for prolonging the period of seed decay and predation. The lack of

307 soil disturbance, the poor light penetration through the canopy and the ability of green manure crops
308 to regrow after cutting are all factors that prevent the establishment of annual weeds (Davies et al.
309 1997; Lawson et al. 1994). The three annual cuttings and removals of the aboveground plant
310 material also played a role in preventing annual weeds from shedding seeds. However, the
311 importance of this biomass removal was minor as most annual weeds disappeared after the first cut
312 in the first year of the green manure. Thereafter, very few annual weeds occurred and then only in
313 bare patches of the plant stand. Aboveground weed biomass in the cash crops explained the content
314 of the seed bank when averaging the biomass across the entire rotation cycle (2011-2015).
315 Nevertheless, weed biomass was not a particularly strong indicator of seed content, despite other
316 studies finding strong correlations between weed biomass and seed production (Lutman, 2002).
317 Weed biomass was not particularly well described in this study due to considerable variation among
318 treatments, which stems from the use of a relatively small sample size. Large seed rains from
319 vigorous weed growth may not necessarily lead to marked seedling recruitment in subsequent years
320 (Sjursen 2001; Webster et al. 2003) since many other factors affect the viability of seeds that have
321 entered the seed bank. Even so, rotation O2 had generally less weed biomass in the annual cash
322 crops than O4, presumably with less impact on crop yield.

323 Predominantly broadleaved weed species were depleted during the green manure phase of O2,
324 whether the species were pure summer annuals, for example *C. album* and *Polygonum aviculare* L.,
325 or had both summer and winter annual growth behaviours, such as *S. media*, *Veronica spp.* and *C.*
326 *bursa-pastoris* (Håkansson, 2003). This was also observed by Albrecht (2005) who found that only
327 the two perennial species *Elytrigia repens* (L.) Nevski and *Taraxacum officinale* F.H. Wigg
328 benefited from the cultivation of grass-clover. Seeds of *T. officinale*, which with its low stature with
329 leaves placed in prostrate rosettes makes it resistant to cutting, were also more numerous in this
330 study where green manure crops had been grown. The grass species recorded were mainly believed

331 to belong to the genus *Poa*, although reliable species identification was difficult at the time of
332 counting. The grasses were too small for precise enumeration at species level, but *Poa annua* L.
333 appeared to be most numerous, followed by *Poa trivialis* L. The ability for prostrate growth and
334 seed production in spite of the grass cuts probably allowed the grass populations (and *T. officinale*)
335 to increase under green manure crops, as suggested by Teasdale et al. (2004). The *Poa*-species were
336 also the only ones responding consistently to cover crops with lower seed numbers where cover
337 crops were grown. The lack of tillage when cover crops were present prevented the stimulation of
338 new seed germination, and seeds shed on the soil surface from the weed plants present were likely
339 to be exposed to significant seed loss (Jensen, 2010). In the situation without cover crops, *P. annua*
340 especially is likely to have thrived so quickly that plants succeeded in shedding seeds between
341 cultivation events (Warwick, 1979). Cultivation worked in two ways by stimulating new seed
342 germination while preserving newly shed seeds through soil incorporation where they are less
343 exposed to seed loss. This in combination may have promoted the build-up of *P. annua* populations
344 through sequential generations over a short time.

345 The legacy effect of the green manure crops on the weed seed bank was still significant three
346 years after termination, thus supporting the hypothesis that green manure crops would reduce the
347 seed bank for at least three years. The seed bank of O2 was 41 % lower than that of O4 three years
348 after termination of the green manure crop when comparing the average of the cover crop
349 treatments for EP3 and O2 in Fig. 3 with the main effect of O4 in Table 5. However, the legacy
350 fertility effect from green manure crops will only last one to three years (Sørensen et al., 2014; Shah
351 et al., 2017), eventually causing crops to become less suppressive against weeds. Weed seed rain is
352 thus likely to increase, which may enhance weed augmentation beyond three years after termination
353 of a green manure crop.

354 The National Danish Advisory Centre (SEGES) advocates 20 % of leguminous green manure
355 crops in organic arable cropping systems with limited access to animal manures. This will increase
356 the crop supply of N and help maintain soil fertility, and calculations justify the economic
357 feasibility of green manuring (SEGES, personal communication). It would require eight years of
358 annual cash crops for a two-year leguminous green manure crop to make up 20 % of a crop
359 sequence. Eight years of cash crops with successful weed control would increase the seed bank to
360 7,700 seeds m⁻², according to the extrapolation of Eq. (4), which is still well below the magnitude of
361 approximately 11,000 seeds m⁻² of rotation O4 with annual cash crops only (main effect for O4 in
362 Table 5). The lower weed pressure following green manuring benefits subsequent crops by reducing
363 weed interference and is particularly important for minimising the financial burden of hand-
364 weeding in organic row crops (Melander and Rasmussen, 2001). Previous studies have also shown
365 that green manure crops suitable for mowing can substantially suppress the perennial weed species
366 *Cirsium arvense* (L.) Scop. (Melander et al., 2016) and *Sonchus arvensis* L. (Melander, unpublished
367 data). The rhizomatous grass species *E. repens* is an exception that may proliferate during periods
368 with leys (Melander et al., 2016). Thus, the planning of crop rotations needs to allow for periods in
369 which effective mechanical control campaigns against *E. repens*, such as summer fallowing or post-
370 harvest cultivations, can be employed (Rasmussen et al., 2014).

371

372 **5. Conclusions**

373

374 A biennial leguminous green manure crop can substantially reduce the seed bank of annual
375 weeds in subsequent spring-sown annual cash crops, as seen for rotation O2 in this study. At the
376 time at which the green manure crop was terminated, the weed seed bank in O2 was 65 % lower
377 than the seed bank of rotation O4 with annual spring-sown cash crops only. The legacy effect was

378 still present three years after termination; the seed bank of O2 was 41 % lower than that of O4. Seed
379 bank depletion following a green manure crop was seen for both summer and winter annual weed
380 species, as well as those having both growth characteristics. The results add to the benefits of
381 including whole-year green manure crops in organic crop rotations that have limited access to
382 animal manures. A green manure crop not only helps improve soil fertility, but can also reduce
383 weed problems in annual cash crops that follow periods with green manure crops.

384

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395

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Table 1

The crops grown in the four entries of crop rotations O2 and O4 at Foulumgaard during the 2011-2015 cropping cycle. ‘+M’ denotes actual manure N applications (kg total-N ha⁻¹), with target N rates in parentheses for each crop. Crops succeeded by a cover crop (CC) are shown with a ‘+’.

Rotation	Year	Entry 1			Entry 2			Entry 3			Entry 4		
		Crops	+M	CC	Crops	+M	CC	Crops	+M	CC	Crops	+M	CC
O2	2011	S. wheat	100 (100)	+	Potato	100 (100)	+	Lucerne	0		S. barley:ley	60 (60)	
	2012	Potato	87 (100)	+	S. barley:ley	52 (60)		Lucerne	0		Lucerne	0	
	2013	S. barley:ley	56 (60)		Lucerne	0		S. wheat	96 (100)	+	Lucerne	0	
	2014	Grass-clover	0		Lucerne	0		Potato	79 (100)	+	S. wheat	79 (100)	+
	2015	Grass-clover	0		S. wheat	99 (110)	+	S. barley:ley	54 (60)		Oat	99 (110)	+
O4	2011	S. wheat	100 (100)	+	Hemp	90 (90)		S. barley	60 (60)	+	Potato	100 (100)	+
	2012	Potato	87 (100)	+	Pea:barley	0	+	Hemp	78 (90)		S. barley	52 (60)	+
	2013	S. barley	56 (60)	+	S. wheat	96 (100)	+	Pea:barley	0	+	Hemp	79 (90)	
	2014	Hemp	81 (90)		Potato	79 (100)	+	S. wheat	79 (100)	+	Pea:barley	0	+
	2015	Faba bean	0	+	S. barley	54 (60)	+	Oat	99 (110)	+	S. wheat	99 (110)	+

Table 2

Arithmetic means of each weed species and of weed seeds in total recorded in the seed bank of crop rotations O2 and O4. SE is the standard error of the mean and *n* is the number of observations.

Weed species	Crop rotation					
	O2			O4		
	Mean (no m ⁻²)	<i>n</i>	SE	Mean (no m ⁻²)	<i>n</i>	SE
<i>Poa</i> spp. L.	1662	16	320	961	16	188
<i>Stellaria media</i> (L.) Vill.	644	16	125	4752	16	1352
<i>Veronica</i> spp. L.	606	16	121	2186	16	512
<i>Capsella bursa-pastoris</i> (L.) Medik.	491	16	197	616	16	146
<i>Viola arvensis</i> Murray	280	16	106	372	16	137
<i>Fallopia convolvulus</i> (L.) Á. Löve	238	16	100	267	16	49
<i>Lamium purpureum</i> L.	206	16	64	297	16	85
<i>Persicaria</i> spp. (L.) Mill.	195	16	99	272	16	113
<i>Taraxacum officinale</i> F.H. Wigg	181	16	120	14	16	14
<i>Tripleurospermum perforatum</i> (Mérat) M. Láinz	149	16	52	268	16	72
<i>Aphanes arvensis</i> L.	137	16	54	29	16	29
<i>Myosotis arvensis</i> (L.) Hill	119	16	38	194	16	67
<i>Juncus bufonius</i> L.	90	16	30	134	16	44
<i>Papaver rhoeas</i> L.	59	16	59	0	16	0
<i>Polygonum aviculare</i> L.	45	16	24	361	16	154
<i>Cirsium</i> spp. Miller	45	16	33	135	16	38
<i>Cardamine hirsute</i> L.	45	16	33	30	16	21
<i>Gnaphalium uliginosum</i> L.	44	16	32	258	16	75
<i>Galeopsis</i> spp. L.	44	16	32	60	16	35
<i>Chenopodium album</i> L.	43	16	23	310	16	156
<i>Plantago major</i> L.	31	16	21	89	16	74
<i>Senecio vulgaris</i> L.	31	16	21	61	16	27
<i>Atriplex patula</i> L.	16	16	16	139	16	79
<i>Fumaria officinalis</i> L.	15	16	15	58	16	45
<i>Spergula arvensis</i> L.	15	16	15	29	16	20
<i>Arabidopsis thaliana</i> (L.) Heynh.	15	16	15	16	16	16
<i>Echinochloa crus-galli</i> (L.) P. Beauv.	15	16	15	15	16	15
<i>Epilobium montanum</i> L.	15	16	15	15	16	15
<i>Raphanus raphanistrum</i> L.	0	16	0	30	16	30
Weed seeds in total	5475	16	392	11967	16	1466

Table 3

Significant effects of crop rotation (O2 and O4) and entry point (1 to 4) on weed species richness, the Shannon's diversity index (H_{SH}) and the Shannon's evenness index (E_{SH}). Least squares means (LSMs) with back-transformed values in parentheses are shown for each level of the two factors. SE are standard errors of LSMs.

Variables	Effects	Levels	LSMs	SE	Significance between levels (Tukey test)
<i>Species richness</i>	Crop rotation (CR), $P = 0.0024$	O2	8.6	0.78	O2 vs. O4, $P = 0.0214$
		O4	11.4	0.78	
H_{SH}	CR x Entry point (EP), $P = 0.0011$	O2-1	0.29 (1.8)	0.031	O2-1 vs. O2-2, $P = 0.9776$
		O2-2	0.34 (2.0)	0.031	O2-1 vs. O2-3, $P = 0.9961$
		O2-3	0.26 (1.7)	0.031	O2-1 vs. O2-4, $P = 0.9928$
		O2-4	0.26 (1.6)	0.031	O2-2 vs. O2-3, $P = 0.7165$
					O2-2 vs. O2-4, $P = 0.6724$
					O2-3 vs. O2-4, $P = 1.0000$
		O4-1	0.36 (2.1)	0.031	O4-1 vs. O4-2, $P = 0.0086$
		O4-2	0.18 (1.2)	0.031	O4-1 vs. O4-3, $P = 0.9977$
		O4-3	0.33 (2.0)	0.031	O4-1 vs. O4-4, $P = 1.0000$
		O4-4	0.37 (2.2)	0.031	O4-2 vs. O4-3, $P = 0.0379$
					O4-2 vs. O4-4, $P = 0.0058$
					O4-3 vs. O4-4, $P = 0.9911$
E_{SH}	CR x EP, $P = 0.0015$	O2-1	0.37 (0.54)	0.041	O2-1 vs. O2-2, $P = 0.9699$
		O2-2	0.42 (0.60)	0.041	O2-1 vs. O2-3, $P = 0.9949$
		O2-3	0.33 (0.49)	0.041	O2-1 vs. O2-4, $P = 0.9919$
		O2-4	0.32 (0.49)	0.041	O2-2 vs. O2-3, $P = 0.6770$
					O2-2 vs. O2-4, $P = 0.6419$
					O2-3 vs. O2-4, $P = 1.0000$
		O4-1	0.46 (0.63)	0.041	O4-1 vs. O4-2, $P = 0.0099$
		O4-2	0.22 (0.36)	0.041	O4-1 vs. O4-3, $P = 0.9954$
		O4-3	0.42 (0.59)	0.041	O4-1 vs. O4-4, $P = 1.0000$
		O4-4	0.47 (0.64)	0.041	O4-2 vs. O4-3, $P = 0.0423$
					O4-2 vs. O4-4, $P = 0.0074$
					O4-3 vs. O4-4, $P = 0.9870$

Table 4

Significant effects of crop rotation (CR), entry point (EP), and cover crop (CC) and their interactions on the log-transformed number of germinable weed seeds (no. m⁻²) of the following variables: seeds in total m⁻², *Stellaria media*, *Veronica spp.*, *Poa spp.* and *Capsella bursa-pastoris*.

DF = degrees of freedom and DDF = denominator degrees of freedom

Variables	Factors	DF	DDF	F-value	Level of significance
Weed seeds in total (no m ⁻²)	Crop rotation (CR)	1	16	29432.5	<i>P</i> < 0.0001
	Entry point (EP)	3	1	1179.9	<i>P</i> = 0.0214
	Cover crop (CC)	1	16	498.3	<i>P</i> < 0.0001
	CR x EP	3	1	1926.3	<i>P</i> = 0.0167
	CC x EP	3	1	2291.3	<i>P</i> = 0.0154
	CR x CC	1	16	953.2	<i>P</i> < 0.0001
	CR x EP x CC	3	1	1361.2	<i>P</i> = 0.0199
<i>Stellaria media</i> (no m ⁻²)	Crop rotation (CR)	1	19	23507.7	<i>P</i> < 0.0001
	Entry point (EP)	3	1	1334.8	<i>P</i> = 0.0201
	Cover crop (CC)	1	19	1365.9	<i>P</i> < 0.0001
	CR x EP	3	1	1942.5	<i>P</i> = 0.0167
	CC x EP	3	1	3585.3	<i>P</i> = 0.0123
	CR x CC	1	19	851.1	<i>P</i> < 0.0001
<i>Veronica spp.</i> (no m ⁻²)	Crop rotation (CR)	1	16	6744.3	<i>P</i> < 0.0001
	Entry point (EP)	3	1	1363.1	<i>P</i> = 0.0199
	Cover crop (CC)	1	16	1124.8	<i>P</i> < 0.0001
	CR x EP	3	1	641.0	<i>P</i> = 0.0290
	CC x EP	3	1	584.6	<i>P</i> = 0.0304
	CR x CC	1	16	13.8	<i>P</i> = 0.0019
	CR x EP x CC	3	1	815.0	<i>P</i> = 0.0257
<i>Poa spp.</i> (no m ⁻²)	Crop rotation (CR)	1	16	563.8	<i>P</i> < 0.0001
	Entry point (EP)	3	1	2714.4	<i>P</i> = 0.0141
	Cover crop (CC)	1	16	2494.6	<i>P</i> < 0.0001
	CR x EP	3	1	114.3	<i>P</i> = 0.0220
	CC x EP	3	1	217.0	<i>P</i> = 0.0498
	CR x CC	1	16	124.6	<i>P</i> < 0.0001
	CR x EP x CC	3	1	443.0	<i>P</i> = 0.0349
<i>Capsella bursa-pastoris</i> (no m ⁻²)	Crop rotation (CR)	1	19	481.9	<i>P</i> < 0.0001
	Entry point (EP)	3	1	676.6	<i>P</i> = 0.0283
	Cover crop (CC)	1	19	1669.0	<i>P</i> < 0.0001
	CR x EP	3	1	304.3	<i>P</i> = 0.0421
	CC x EP	3	1	595.4	<i>P</i> = 0.0301

Table 5

Main effects of crop rotation (CR), entry point (EP) and cover crop (CC) with least squares means (LSM) of germinable weed seeds (no. m⁻²) shown for each level of the three factors. SE are standard errors of LSMs.

Factor	Level	LSM (weed seed no. m ⁻²)	SE	Relative to level 1 (%)	Significance between levels (Tukey test)
CR	O2	5347	46.3	-	1 vs. 2, $P < 0.0001$
	O4	11094	92.2	+ 107	
EP	1	6213	57.5	-	1 vs. 2, $P = 0.0202$
	2	8913	79.6	+ 43	1 vs. 3, $P = 0.0339$
	3	7718	69.1	+ 24	1 vs. 4, $P = 0.0255$
	4	8235	73.0	+ 33	2 vs. 3, $P = 0.0470$ 2 vs. 4, $P = 0.0833$ 3 vs. 4, $P = 0.1024$
CC	Without	8077	68.4	-	1 vs. 2, $P < 0.0001$
	With	7345	62.4	- 9	

Table 6

Estimates of the number of germinable weed seeds in the seed bank SB at the end of the leguminous green manure crop period and the rate b of increase in the seed bank with the increasing number of years since the green manure crop was terminated. Parameters SB and b were estimated according to Eq. (4) and were not affected by cover crop treatment (-CC, +CC). SE is the standard error of estimates.

Cover crop	SB (germinable seeds m ⁻²)	SE	b	SE
- CC, +CC	3935	666	0.3932	0.2977

Table 7

Effects of crop rotation (CR), entry point (EP), and cover crop (CC) and their interactions on the square root transformed amount of aboveground weed biomass (g m^{-2}) averaging the five-year rotation cycle. DF = degrees of freedom and DDF = denominator degrees of freedom.

Factors	DF	DDF	F-value	Level of significance
Crop rotation (CR)	1	46.9	13.45	$P = 0.0006$
Entry point (EP)	3	47.1	6.42	$P = 0.0010$
Cover crop (CC)	1	45.0	7.08	$P = 0.0108$
CR x EP	3	47.1	4.45	$P = 0.0078$
CC x EP	3	44.7	1.30	$P = 0.2860$
CR x CC	1	45.0	3.18	$P = 0.0814$
CR x EP x CC	3	44.7	0.06	$P = 0.9791$

Figure legends

Fig. 1. Germinable weed seeds shown for the three-factor interaction crop rotation x entry point x cover crop. Means are back-transformed means from log-transformation. Columns with similar letters are not significantly different. The columns are shown for the different entry points (EP1 to EP4), and the codes below the columns represent the crops during the years 2011 to 2015 (see also Table 1).

Fig. 2. The relationship between the number of germinable weed seeds and number of years since termination of the green manure crop in rotation O2. Observed values are averages of the two cover crop levels, and the error bars represent the standard errors.

Fig. 3. Aboveground weed biomass averaging the five-year rotation cycle and shown for the three-factor interaction crop rotation x entry point x cover crop. Means are back-transformed means from square root transformation. Columns with similar letters are not significantly different. The columns are shown for the different entry points (EP1 to EP4), and the codes below the columns represent the crops during the years 2011 to 2015 (see also Table 1).

Fig. 4. The general relationship between the number of germinable weed seeds and aboveground weed biomass averaged across the years 2011, 2012, 2013, 2014 and 2015. Observed values are means of each level of crop rotation x cover crop x entry point, totalling 16 observations.

Fig. 1

Fig. 2

Fig. 3

Fig. 4